

SURVIVORS OF NIPAH VIRUS ATTACK IN KERALA: AN INTERPRETATIVE PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

**M.Phil. Dissertation
SUBMITTED TO**

**KERALA UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES [KUHS]
THRISSUR – 680 596, KERALA**

**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR
M.Phil. DEGREE IN PSYCHIATRIC SOCIAL WORK**

BY

AKHILA PRABHAKAR

DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHIATRIC SOCIAL WORK

**INSTITUTE OF MENTAL HEALTH AND NEUROSCIENCES
[IMHANS]
AUTONOMOUS INSTITUTE UNDER GOVT. OF KERAGOV'T. MEDICAL
COLLEGE CAMPUS, KOZHIKODE-673 008**

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the present study entitled "**Survivors Of Nipah Virus Attack In Kerala: An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis**" has been conducted by me at the Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences (IMHANS), Govt. Medical College Campus, Kozhikode, under the guidance of Dr. G.Ragesh, Lecturer of Psychiatric Social Work, Dr. Abdul Salam K.P, Head, Department of Clinical Psychology [Co-Guide] and Dr.Chandni R, Head [Co-Guide], Department of Emergency Medicine, Government Medical College, Calicut.

This dissertation is being submitted to the Kerala University of Health Sciences (KUHS) in partial fulfilment of the requirements of Master of Philosophy in Psychiatric social work.

I further declare that this is an original study and no part of it has been published or submitted to any university previously.

Date:

AKHILA PRABHAKAR

DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHIATRIC SOCIAL WORK

Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences (IMHANS)

Autonomous Institute under Govt. Of Kerala

Govt. Medical College Campus, Kozhikode-673 008

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that **AKHILA PRABHAKAR** is a bonafide student of the Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences (IMHANS), Govt. Medical College Campus, Kozhikode, pursuing of M.Phil Degree in Psychiatric Social Work under Kerala University of Health Science (KUHS) for the academic session 2018-2020. She has carried out this study entitled "**Survivors Of Nipah Virus Attack In Kerala:An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis**" at the Institute under my supervision. This dissertation is hereby approved for submission to Kerala University of Health Sciences (KUHS) as partial fulfilment of the requirements of M.Phil. Degree in Psychiatric social Work.

Dr.G Ragesh

(GUIDE)

Lecturer

Department of Psychiatric Social Work

IMHANS Kozhikode

Dr. Abdul Salam K.P

(CO-GUIDE)

Head,

Department of Clinical Psychology

IMHANS Kozhikode

Dr.Chandni R

(Co-Guide)

Head, Department of Emergency Medicine

Government Medical College Kozhikode

Dr.P Krishnakumar

Director

IMHANS Kozhikode

Acknowledgement

At this moment of accomplishment, it is an honour to express my heartfelt thanks to all those who have contributed in many ways to the success of the study.

First and foremost, I would like to thank God for providing me this opportunity and making it possible for me to accomplish my dream of MPhil degree from IMHANS.

I would like to express my deepest sense of gratitude to my guide Dr.G Ragesh Lecturer of Psychiatric Social Work, IMHANS, for all his guidance throughout the period of this study.

I express my sincere thanks to my Co- guide Dr.Abdul Salam K.P, Head, Department of Clinical Psychology, IMHANS, for his thoughtful guidance and suggestions during this research work.

I would like to thanksto my Co- guide Dr.Chandni R, Head, Department of Emergency Medicine, Government Medical College, Kozhikode for her various suggestions and help throughout my study.

My gratitude to Dr. Krishnakumar P, Director, IMHANS for giving me opportunity to pursue my research and providing all the instrumental facilities.

I take this opportunity to thank all my friends for the immense help and support provided although my study.

Last but not least, my heartfelt gratitude to my parents who are the greatest inspiration in my life. You have showed keen interest in all aspects of my life for who I am right now.

AKHILA PRABHAKAR

CONTENTS

Sl. No	Contents	Page. No
	Abstract	1
1.	Introduction	2 - 7
2.	Review of Literature	8 - 18
3.	Methodology	19 - 23
4.	Results	24 - 38
5.	Discussion	39 - 45
6.	Summary and conclusion	46 - 48
7.	Reference	49 - 53
	Appendices	

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title of the Tables	Page No
3.1	Steps used for analysing the data.	19 - 21

Abstract

Introduction: The first Nipah outbreak was reported in the Kozhikode district of Kerala, India in 2018 May. Twenty-one deaths were recorded among a total of 23 cases. Those who have died were mainly from the districts of Kozhikode and Malappuram districts. Two of the infected were survived. By the end of May 2019 a young student was confirmed with Nipah in Ernakulam district of Kerala and recovered after 2 months of treatment. No significant casualties related to Nipah have been in the second outbreak till now and the infection seems contained due to the early identification and caution by health department of Kerala Government.

Methods: The present study focuses on first hand experiences of survivors of Nipah virus attack happened in 2018 and 2019, in state of Kerala. The qualitative study uses the method of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). Sample of three subjects (All Nipah survivors) was collected using Purposive Sampling Method. Data collected by semi structured interviews through phone calls.

Result: The major themes emerged out the study were; The dimension of distance, Minimization and denial, Being a patient, Fantasies and emotional reasoning, Search for a secure base and Profound nature of the experience.

Conclusion: This present study focuses on the experiences of Survivors of Kerala Nipah virus attack identified six super ordinate themes; The dimension of distance, Minimization and denial, Fantasies and emotional reasoning, Search for a secure base, Being a patient and Profound nature of the experience. This study indicates Psychosocial interventions for patients and their family members for during and after the hospitalization.

Keywords: phenomenology, Nipah virus, trauma, pandemic

INTRODUCTION

Nipah virus is a zoonotic virus. It is transmitted from animals to humans and can also be transmitted through contaminated food or directly between people. In infected people, it causes a range of illnesses from asymptomatic infection to acute respiratory illness and fatal encephalitis (1). This study aims to understand how the survivors of this deadly virus made sense of their experience during the period. In this chapter, the various aspects of the topic is discussed.

Nipah virus infection (NiV) is an emerging highly pathogenic zoonotic disease, outbreaks of which have been reported from South East Asian countries. The virus belongs to the genus *Henipaviral* and subfamily *Paramyxoviridae*. The natural reservoirs of the virus are found from the fruit bats. Human infection begins with fever and brain inflammation leading to disorientation or coma and some patients suffered with acute respiratory distress syndrome (1). In humans, the infection can cause severe and often fatal disease. Once infected with Nipah virus, humans can transmit the virus to other humans (2).

Nipah virus in Asian countries

Nipah virus has caused only a few known outbreaks in Asia, it infects a wide range of animals and causes severe disease and death in people. Outbreaks of NiV have been reported from Malaysia, Singapore and India. Direct contact with infected pigs was the mode of transmission in the first outbreak in Malaysia in 1999, during that time, a total of 283 Nipah human cases were identified 109 of those where

fatal (3). No new outbreaks have been reported in Malaysia since then. During this time, as a result of pigs imported from Malaysia, the disease also affected people in Singapore,. the infection spread to abattoir workers in Singapore. most human infections resulted from direct contact with sick pigs or their contaminated tissues. This outbreak lasted from September 1998 to May 1999 (4), Transmission is thought to have occurred via unprotected exposure to secretions from the pigs, or unprotected contact with the tissue of a sick animal. resulting in over 900,000 culled pigs to control the outbreak (5). The Malaysia outbreak was linked to fruit trees at large commercial farms, where bats dropped partially eaten contaminated fruits and pigs ate them, got the infection, and later transmitted the infection to their caregivers (6).

It was also recognized in Bangladesh in 2001, and nearly annual outbreaks have occurred in that country since. Other regions may be at risk for infection, as evidence of the virus has been found in the known natural reservoir (*Pteropus* bat species) and several other bat species in a number of countries, including Cambodia, Ghana, Indonesia, Madagascar, the Philippines, and Thailand. During the later outbreaks in Bangladesh, Nipah virus spread directly from human-to-human through close contact with people's secretions and excretions (1).

Nipah virus in India

The outbreak of NiV have been reported from India were linked to consumption of fresh date palm sap contaminated by fruit bats. The first evidence of human-to-human transmission was seen in Siliguri, West Bengal, India (2001) where

hospital visitors and health workers contracted the infection after exposure to patients, indicating transmission in health-care setting.

The first recorded outbreak of NiV infection in India, affecting 66 persons with a mortality of 68%, occurred in Siliguri, West Bengal, in 2001, The second, affecting 5 persons with 100% mortality, was in Nadia, West Bengal, in 2007. NiV infection was designated one of 10 priority diseases in the World Health Organization Research and Development Blueprint of 2018. (8)

Kerala scenario

Nipah virus has been affected people in Kerala in the middle of May 2018. The first case was reported from Kozhikode. There have been 21 individuals died and 2 survived out of 23cases, in that, 5 cases were not clinically confirmed. In 18 confirmed cases, including 17 deaths has been reported in Kozhikode and Malappuram districts in 2018. In second outbreak in 2019, one person has infected and he survived with the help of medical science. No other cases reported that year.

In the first outbreak, a family cluster of encephalitis cases were reported. A 28-year-old boy with encephalitis were admitted in private facility in Kozhikode district on May 17th 2018. His family members including father and aunt also developed fever, body ache and vomiting on the same day. His brother had died following a similar illness 12 days earlier.

Kerala had a rapid spread of the NiV coupled with equally alarming speed of spread of rumors, misinformation, and fake news about the disease. All efforts of Kerala's health-care system were made to ensure that no more lives are lost. The government was prompt in handling the outbreak with utmost seriousness. The efficient action of the state was well appreciated. In spite of that, the professionals, community, and the government faced an unexpected challenge in the form of rumors which spiraled into a mass anxiety that crossed beyond the affected district to the entire state and even reached the neighboring states which had the potential to affect daily lives of the millions. Social media played a role in circulating information about epidemic outbreaks whereas false news also spread through resulting in mass panic and anxiety of the people. The role of social media in creating false information on the fatality rate created panic among the population. (9).

This situation created panic and confusion among the health workers and the general public. The doctors, nurses, and staff in the hospitals where these patients had been treated before diagnostic confirmation were apprehensive over their chances of contracting the illness (10).

Psychosocial Effects

Psychological effects are one of the most important repercussion of virus attacks, the prompt action ensured containing the spread of Nipah outbreak and halting a major catastrophe, in spite of the best efforts the anxiety and panic was commonly

reported among the communities. Many researchers have found that the diseases leave significant psychological trauma on the survivors. And It is important to understand that any illness can bring physical, psychological, social, and economic impact among people. Nipah had widespread impact on human population not only biologically as well as psychosocially. Its rapid onset created panic situations among the population(11). Unlike the physical issues, the impact of the deadly virus on psychosocial wellbeing is not very much attended in Indian population. The study by Lithin, Z., Hari Krishnan, U. et al (10) Psychosocial Perspective of Nipah Virus Outbreak in Kerala, they found that there is no literature found on psychosocial impact on Nipah, and in limited studies, the authors collected and collated various reactions reported in newspapers, publications and reports during Nipah outbreak in Kerala. The most commonly reported psychosocial reactions were panic, fear, social disruptions, and economic loss across the region. The sudden virus attack resulted in death and affecting hundreds also resulted in widespread panic and closure of business and educational establishments.

The 2018 outbreak in Kerala overtly focused on the public health mitigation and prevention aspects, the psychosocial reactions warrant a multifaceted approach to address the psychosocial consequences of this epidemic at individual, family, and community/state levels. The basic upshot of this strikes that all these are fully interconnected and have a cyclic effect on each other. Therefore, intervention in one area will help to bring change in other areas and also in developing a holistic care model. For instance, if a person who is the breadwinner of family is

hospitalized due to the virus infection, it is not only affecting the individual but also has an effect on his or her familial life. Thus, the focus needs to be shifted at looking an ill person from biomedical perspective of disease to a biopsychosocial (BPS) perspective of health. The emphasis of BPS approach is placed on achieving positive health and preventing dysfunctions across all the areas of person's lives, in addition, to mitigate psychological distress and reducing symptomatology (12). The importance of providing authentic and adequate information, community engagement, sensitization of the community, psychosocial analysis of the situation, resource mobilization, preventive activities, and enhancing social supports is some of the strategies to improve the quality of life of the affected.

Currently, the impact of psychosocial factors caused by Nipah virus has not been explored. An interpretative approach for understanding the issues they faced, or the coping mechanisms employed by Nipah survivors to overcome psychosocial challenges during and after the virus attack is also lacking. A deeper understanding of these issues can help policy makers, practitioners and health system workers design and tailor future health interventions to address the unmet psychosocial needs of Nipah survivors. To fill this existing gap in knowledge, it is important to understand the psychological factors played a role of people who have survived the virus attack. An in-depth analysis of those factors will help us understand the phenomenon including the psychosocial characteristics of people who experienced it better and will direct us to future studies and intervention.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

When it comes to existing literature, one realizes how little researchers have chosen IPA as a methodology in understanding psychological phenomenon. There exist very few studies on Nipah viral attack or any other viral diseases that make use of IPA or Qualitative methods in general. However, there are some researches in the area of health and trauma. In this chapter, the review of previous literature is discussed under the following headlines:

- NIPAH related studies
- Other qualitative researches on Disease and Trauma
- Other Related Researches

NIPAH Related Studies

Lithin Z, Harikrishnan U, Jayakumar C, Sekar K, (10) explored the Psychosocial Perspective of Nipah Virus Outbreak in Kerala, it focused on the psychosocial care interventions for the virus and misinformation and stigma towards the family members of the infected people. They found that the Primary focus of any public health issue is the prevention and mitigation of the illness spreading to a larger population with the help of advanced holistic health care. The prompt intervention of the stakeholders limited the diseases spread and contained larger impact reflects proactive, systematic, and coordinated efforts can change the scenario. Their recommendation was in response to the challenges such as Nipah outbreak, the stakeholders, government, professionals, and administration, first responders need

to be aware of the psychosocial impact and care and the response and mitigation plans must include the psychosocial intervention and a proper capacity building and awareness to health first responders, those who are in charge of the management of the outbreak and public health would enhance their capacity to respond and face any eventuality in this age of misinformation and fake news. And they tried to categorize the psychosocial impact of Nipah among people in three domains such as individual, familial and to the community and state.

S.S Swathy, Midhun Sidharthan, Muhammed Issudeen, T.M Shibukumar, Ashok Kumar, Harish M Tharayil (13) provided Psychological interventions during Nipah outbreak in Kozhikode district which was based mainly on the health education regarding the illness and nature of disease transmission. For this they launched a telephonic Nipah mental health helpline by the government to reach common people and out patients based support was provided. The team provided Benzodiazepines and relaxation techniques for the needy. And as a result of the telephonic helpline, a total of 145 calls were received till June 2018 and almost 28 people required psychological interventions in the form of brief supportive psychotherapy and relaxation techniques including JPMR and they also found that Inadequate information regarding illness exaggerated the risk perception among common people.

Other Qualitative Researches on Disease and Trauma

Engel, N., Ganesh, G., Patil, M., Yellappa, V., Pai, N. P., Vadnais, C., & Pai, M. (14) conducted an exploratory qualitative study, with 78 semi-structured

interviews and 13 focus group discussions in an urban and rural area of Karnataka, India, with healthcare providers (doctors, nurses, specialists, traditional healers, and informal providers), patients, community health workers, test manufacturers, laboratory technicians, program managers and policy-makers. Participants were purposively sampled to represent settings of hospitals, peripheral labs, clinics, communities and homes, in both the public and private sectors. They identified three overarching themes affecting point-of-care testing: the main theme is ‘relationships’ among providers and between providers and patients, influenced by the cross-cutting theme of ‘infrastructure’. They state that even if tests can be conducted on the spot and infrastructure challenges have been resolved, relationships among providers and between patients and providers are crucial for successful point-of-care testing. Furthermore, these barriers do not act in isolation, but are interlinked and need to be examined as such. Also, a test alone has only limited power to overcome those difficulties. Test developers, policy-makers, healthcare providers and funders need to use these insights in overcoming barriers to point-of-care testing programs.

Gardner, P. J., & Moallem, P (15) conducted a study on SARS victims. Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) has been labelled a mental health catastrophe, an infectious atypical pneumonia condition that spread to 29 countries in 2002/2003, infecting over 8,000 people, 774 of whom died. They conducted a literature search on electronic databases, including MEDLINE, PsycINFO, CINAHL, and Cochrane Library to conduct a critical review of the English

language literature on the psychological impact of SARS for survivors. Twenty original studies pertaining to the psychological experience of patients revealed prominent symptoms: in the acute and early recovery stages, psychotic symptomatology, fear for survival, and fear of infecting others; across all timeframes, stigmatization, reduced quality of life, and psychological distress; posttraumatic stress symptoms were prevalent across all stages post-SARS. Health care workers with SARS were found to be at increased risk. Limitations within many studies restrict the optimal usefulness of the findings. Studies included in our review consistently reported high rates of emotional distress among survivors, persisting for years post-infection.

Ventura-Garcia, L., Roura, M., Pell, C., Posada, E., Gascón, J., Aldasoro, E., ... & Pool, R. (16) carried out a systematic review aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of qualitative research on Chagas disease, both in endemic and non-endemic countries. Searches were carried out in ten databases, and the bibliographies of retrieved studies were examined. Data from thirty-three identified studies were extracted, and findings were analyzed and synthesized along key themes. Themes identified for endemic countries included: socio-structural determinants of Chagas disease; health practices; biomedical conceptions of Chagas disease; patient's experience; and institutional strategies adopted. Concerning non-endemic countries, identified issues related to access to health services and health seeking. The emergence and perpetuation of Chagas disease depends largely on socio-cultural aspects influencing health. As most

interventions do not address the clinical, environmental, social and cultural aspects jointly, this explicitly multidimensional approach, incorporating the experiences of those affected is a potential tool for the development of long-term successful programs. They summarized that Social and cultural factors are increasingly recognized as relevant to the likelihood of infection with Chagas disease as well as the health seeking practices of those affected. In response, qualitative methods have been used more often to study such factors. This is the first systematic review to focus on the socio-cultural dimensions of Chagas disease. The findings suggest that transdisciplinary approaches, which incorporate preventive and treatment activities, and consider populations' living conditions and their culturally informed understandings of health, might be a tool to reduce Chagas disease incidence in the long-term.

Walter, F. M., Emery, J., Braithwaite, D., & Marteau, T. M. (17) carried out a meta-ethnographic approach to understand Familial Risk of Common Chronic Diseases. Twenty-two qualitative articles were found after a comprehensive literature search and were critically appraised; 11 were included. A meta-ethnographic approach was used to translate the studies across each other, synthesize the translation, and express the synthesis. A dynamic process emerged by which a personal sense of vulnerability included some features that mirror the medical factors used to assess risk, such as the number of affected relatives. Other features are more personal, such as experience of a relative's disease, sudden or premature death, perceived patterns of illness relating to gender or age at death,

and comparisons between a person and an affected relative. The developing vulnerability is interpreted using personal mental models, including models of disease causation, inheritance, and fatalism. A person's sense of vulnerability affects how that person copes with, and attempts to control, any perceived familial risk. They concluded that persons with a family history of a common chronic disease develop a personal sense of vulnerability that is informed by the salience of their family history and interpreted within their personal models of disease causation and inheritance. Features that give meaning to familial risk may be perceived differently by patients and professionals. This review identifies key areas for health professionals to explore with patients that may improve the effectiveness of communication about disease risk and management.

De Roo et al. (18) conducted a study describing the experiences of 60 survivors of the 1995 Ebola epidemic in Kikwit, Democratic Republic of Congo. The subjects were individually interviewed by another Ebola survivor using a standardized questionnaire in French. Survivors were questioned about their experiences prior to diagnosis, at the beginning of the illness, 5 during the acute phase and during the convalescent period. Fear, denial and shame were their principal initial feelings. After release from hospital, survivors were abandoned by family or friends more often than they had expected. Belief in god was an important aid to all of them. Their most negative experiences were witnessing other people dying in the isolation ward of the Kikwit General Hospital, and the

reluctance of hospital personnel to treat them. The study made recommendations of giving more attention to the psychosocial implications of such an epidemic.

Other Related Researches

Hugo, M., Declerck, H., Fitzpatrick, G., Severy, N., Gbabai, O. B. M., & Decroo, T (19) stated that understanding psychological reactions among EVD survivors may provide relevant information about post-treatment adjustment and possible psychological preventative measures. They, therefore studied the psychological reactions in Ebola Virus Disease survivors following their discharge from an Ebola treatment centre in Sierra Leone. Immediately following discharge, survivors met with the psychologist to discuss their experiences in the case management centre and the challenges they may face returning to their communities. Of 74 survivors discharged in the study period, 24 were followed up at home for a psychological consultation three to four weeks after discharge. During the home visit the psychologist applied an adaptation of the trauma screening questionnaire and explored number of family deaths from Ebola Virus Disease, stigma, the meaning they attached to the causation of their illness and general post illness adjustment. They found that all survivors had lost immediate family members to Ebola Virus Disease. Most (16; 67%) had also witnessed their deaths. Eight (32%) survivors had experienced stigma when returning to their communities. Seventeen (71%) survivors experienced arousal and re-experiencing reactions during the first two days post discharge. Five (21%) reported clinically important post traumatic reactions between three- and four-weeks post discharge predicting a risk of

developing post-traumatic stress disorder. Although this study represents a snapshot of post-traumatic stress reactions observed in Ebola survivors, it does demonstrate the need to consider the likelihood of psychological sequelae in EVD survivors. Long term follow-up of is needed to understand psychological care needs of Ebola survivors.

Chua, S. E., Cheung, V., Cheung, C., McAlonan, G. M., Wong, J. W., Cheung, E. P., ... & Wong, M. K. (20) attempted to quantify stress and the psychological impact of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) on high-risk health care workers (HCWs). They evaluated 271 HCWs from SARS units and 342 healthy control subjects, using the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) to assess stress levels and a structured list of putative psychological effects of SARS to assess its psychological effects. Healthy control subjects were balanced for age, sex, education, parenthood, living circumstances, and lack of health care experience. They found that stress levels were raised in both groups (PSS = 18) but were not relatively increased in the HCWs. HCWs reported significantly more positive (94%, $n = 256$) and more negative psychological effects (89%, $n = 241$) from SARS than did control subjects. HCWs declared confidence in infection-control measures. They found that in HCWs, adaptive responses to stress and the positive effects of infection control training may be protective in future outbreaks and elevated stress in the population may be an important indicator of future psychiatric morbidity.

Reissman, D. B., Arias, I., Whitney, E. A. S., & Taylor, T. H. (21) sought more information about PTSD among the participants in a study. The purpose of the study was to assess the physiological relationship between bioterrorism-related anthrax infection and residual health complaints. Dr Reissman and colleagues found that adult survivors of *Bacillus anthracis* infection had significantly more psychological symptoms and reduced quality of life after 6 months than did a comparison group of patients with sepsis and chronic illness (Details of sample not known). While they did not find evidence to link the persisting health complaints with the anthrax infection or its toxins, the results do indicate that traumatic stress symptoms are prominent and need to be addressed within each survivor's medical, psychiatric, and social system of care. The anthrax survivors most frequently reported high levels of depressive, anxious, obsessive-compulsive, and hostile symptoms. These findings are consistent with those obtained from survivors of criminal assault. The 9 survivors (60%) with clinically relevant distress scores on the Symptom Checklist 90-Revised (transformed global severity index scores ≥ 63) also met screening criteria for possible PTSD derived from the same instrument. However, this PTSD index was created and validated for use with female survivors of sexual assault. Accordingly, they did not examine this index further because it has unknown validity for participants in the study. They claim that it is important to assess for psychiatric comorbidity in those exposed to traumatic events, including posttraumatic stress, other anxiety, and depressive disorders.

Niuniu Sun et al. studied the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during hospitalization(22) by using phenomenological and robust sampling approach. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews, phone calls, or face-to-face interviews using quarantine measures. Data were analyzed using the Colaizzi method. The psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during hospitalization was summarized into five themes. First one is attitudes toward the disease included fear, denial, and stigma during the early stages, which later developed into acceptance in the later stages. Second one is the major source of stress included the viral nature of the disease, quarantine measures, and concerns regarding the health of family members. Thirdly, reactions of body and mind included disease stage-dependent emotional responses, excessive attention to symptoms, rumination, and changes in diet, sleep, and behavior. Fourthly, supportive factors included psychological adjustments, medical care, and family and social support. Finally, the disease resulted in psychological growth and patients viewed problems with gratitude through the cherishing of life, family, bravery, and tenacity. And they also found that Negative emotions dominated during the early stages but gradually gave way to mixed positive and negative emotions.

The findings of a study named ‘Lived experiences of Indian youth amid COVID-19 crisis: An Interpretative phenomenological analysis’ (23) done by Alina suhail et al. did an in-depth analysis of the lived experiences of Indian youth amid COVID-19 crisis and its impact on their mental health by interviewing ten college

going students by using a semi-structured interview schedule to elicit participants' experiences with COVID-19 and the impact it has posed on their mental health. Transcripts were analysed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). Alina suhail et al. identified three master themes that emerged out of their research. Which were: Impact on mental health, Positive experiences and Ways of coping amid the crisis.

METHODOLOGY

Aim of the study:

The study aimed to analyze the firsthand experience of the survivors of “Nipah Virus”

Design:

This study followed Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis to analyze the data. Pietkiewicz & Smith (24).

Sample:

A sample of 3 adults (2 Males and 1 Female) who had suffered and survived the virus attack was selected through Purposive sampling method. Family members of the survivors who do not have the direct experience of the virus attack were excluded from the study for getting a clear-cut verbal outcome.

Methods and Procedure:

Detailed, in depth interviews were conducted to collect information regarding the virus attack, survivors’ experience during the virus attack and how they made sense of their practical experience and is evaluated. A set of semi-structured (open ended) questions were developed by an expert panel including the researcher for covering different aspects of their experience. Transcript (verbatim record of data collection event) of the interview taken through audio call was made along with complete audio record of interaction with the consent of participants. These

transcriptions were evaluated, analyzed and emergent themes were developed according to the model of Pietkiewicz & Smith (24).

Study Setting and Data Collection:

The data was collected from individuals through telephonic interview. All the three respondents are interviewed through audio call. Adequate rapport was built through phone call and purpose of the research is explained to them and cleared their doubts before the initiation of the interview. Three unstructured questions were used for ensuring necessary input, which were created by an expert panel.

The questions were:

Question 1: What was your initial thoughts when you came to know about nipah in news?

Question 2: what was your thoughts and reactions after first symptoms.

Question 3: What was your thoughts after testing positive?

Question 4: How was your experience during hospital days?

Question 5: how was it felt when you came back after tested negative ?

These questions along with necessary probes and prompts were used to collect adequate data. Average length of an interview was 50 minutes.

Process of Analysis: The verbatim of each interview is written down and analyzed by the model of Pietkiewicz & Smith (24). There are a number of stages involved in data analysis and these were used flexibly to help guide the process. The data analysis involved moving from a focus on the individual to a more shared understanding and from a descriptive level to a more interpretative one (25).

The detail description of the procedure is given below.

Stage	Details of processes involved
Reading and Re- Reading	<p>The first stage involves the close examination of one transcript. The material is read again and again. Recollections of the interview and initial comments were noted in an attempt to group these and focus on what was being said.</p>
<p>Interpretation of the data (Conceptual level commenting)</p>	<p>The fourth form of interpretation mentioned by Jonathan A. Smith is used to make sense of what the respondents have said (Smith et al., 2009). Free association and</p>

	<p>supervision was used to reach conclusions about interpretations.</p>
<p>Developing Emergent Themes</p>	<p>Discrete chunks of text are attended in order to recall what was learned through interpretation. Emergent themes were developed to capture and reflect understanding (Smith et al., 2009).</p>
<p>Looking for Connections Across the Themes</p>	<p>In this stage the analysis is structured. Emergent themes were drawn together by identifying common links between them using the concepts of abstraction (similar themes brought together), and function (what function it serves) (Smith et al., 2009).</p>
<p>Moving to Next Case</p>	<p>Now the researcher moves on to the remaining transcripts by the same steps. Each case was approached in its own right and</p>

	allows new themes to be developed.
Looking for Patterns Across Cases	In this stage, connections across cases are sought. Through this process individual emergent themes were relabeled and reconfigured. The subordinate themes were drawn together and this resulted in a number of Super ordinate themes for the group each with a number of related subordinate themes (Smith et al., 2009).

Table 1: Showing the steps used for analyzing the data.

Duration of study: The duration of study was one year.

Analysis: This study used Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis to analyze the data. Pietkiewicz & Smith (24).

Ethical Considerations: The IMHANS Ethics Committee Approval.

Ref. No: IMHANS/IEC/PSWT/2019/033

RESULTS

The results obtained after the analysis of data is described under the following headings:

- Procedure
- Description of the results obtained

Procedure

The research was conducted using the IPA model developed by Pietkiewicz & Smith (Pietkiewicz & Smith, 2014). The sample subjects were interviewed over telephone. The interviews were audio recorded and then the verbatim of the interview is written down to Transcripts. A total of 3 subjects were interviewed during September 2020. The first person (Subject I) was interviewed on 9/9/2018 as telephonic interview. The interview lasted up to 50 minutes. The transcript was written down after 3 days of interview and cross checked by repeated hearing of the audio record. The requirements to be made for the next interview and changes to be made in Probes and Prompts were decided after first interview. The second interview was on 7th October 2020. The third interview was done through telephone on 23rd October, 2020. The third subject were the person survived from the second outbreak. The interviews lasted for 50 minutes. These interviews were also transcribed and the quality of the data found to be adequate as per the evaluation of the experts' panel.

The analysis of the data was initiated after the completion of all the transcripts. Initially the transcript of subject I was analyzed. After the descriptive, linguistic and conceptual commenting explained by the Pietkiewicz & Smith model, Free Association technique was used by the researcher for interpretation of the transcript. The transcript was read over and over and each time significant interpretations were made. While re-reading the

transcript, new interpretations were added. These interpretations were evaluated and grouped into discrete chunks (Subordinate Themes) according to their relevance and interconnectedness in representing similar phenomenon or process. At the next stage, these subordinate themes were then grouped based on their similarities resulting in the development of Super Ordinate Themes. The same process is extended to next transcript.

After the completion of analysis of all the three subjects, the pattern across cases was identified. The similarities and connections between themes across all the transcripts were evaluated and final list of super ordinate themes is made. Each super ordinate theme contained set of subordinate themes and these subordinate themes represent the interpretations made by the researcher, creating an account of a general picture of the entire transcript.

Details of the Samples Collected

- Subject 1: A 35-year-old male who lives with his family. He was the survivor of the nipah virus infection. His wife diseased and deceased due to the same illness and he got affected from her. Later he remarried after one year.
- Subject 2: A 23-year-old female, currently working as a health care worker. She was a student a hospital. She was affected from a Nipah positive patient during her training.
- Subject 3: A 20 years old Male, Degree graduate. He lives with his parents. He was the survivor of the outbreak of Nipah virus. (8, 27).

Description of the Results

After the comprehensive step by step analysis Six Super Ordinate themes has emerged. These are the overview of the themes.

1. The dimension of distance
2. Minimization and denial
3. Being a patient
4. Fantasies and Emotional reasoning
5. Search for a secure base
6. Profound nature of the experience

Theme 1: The Dimension of Distance

This is the first super ordinate theme that emerged after the analysis of the data. It represents the subordinate themes regarding the distancing they experienced on the part of the society, the virus, and even the need to distance themselves from others for fear of getting them contaminated. The subjects related their experience of being socially discriminated from others, of having heard experiences of others being infected, and having to isolated themselves from others.

The following subordinate themes emerged from the data-

1. Distance by others
2. Distance from others

Distance by others

Participants I and III expressed their experience with people outside their home. They experienced a distance kept by others from them, due to the nature of the disease which persisted even after completing their quarantine period. They related their experience of how people would walk away from them, and even ignore their very existence. The participants related experiences of how, following the infection, they had to experience rejection from the society in various domains of their lives, as well as the lives of their family members. Participants also spoke about how the first time they heard about the virus; it was happening to someone somewhere; that they were safe because the virus had infected someone at a distance.

An excerpt from the transcript of participant I read-

“There was a wedding happening in the nearby house, I was passing through and stopped the car for a moment. Seeing me, the people gathered just got up and walked away”.

He also said *“...Even our extended family excluded us during many situations. We all felt like we didn't exist anymore...”*.

The transcript of participant III was also in line with this-

“...The cleaning staff told me that no one even dared to touch my clothes, let alone wash them...”

He also said:

“...This affected my mother’s job. She took leave to take care of me and now they wouldn’t take her back. She lost her job and is still unemployed...”

He further said:

“...When I went back to college, after I’d recovered, that time, they said that I couldn’t continue my course there...”

He had recalled his experience of hearing about Nipah virus for the first time.

He said : *“...I had heard about the nurse in Kozhikode that was infected with the virus, through WhatsApp...”*

Distance from others

Following the infection, the participants had to isolate themselves, both voluntarily as well as forcefully. Participants recalled their experience of having had to stay isolated from others, even their own family, for the risk of contaminating them. They also started to intentionally maintain a distance from others, because people around them were spreading negativity.

An excerpt from the transcript of Participant I read:

“...While going to the hospital, we had to wear masks and keep one meter distance with everyone...There were a lot of people dependent on me, like my mother, father and brothers. If I’m safe, they are also safe...”

He also said- *“I maintained a safe distance even with the sweepers who came to clean the ward, I had to make sure that their family was also safe...”*

He further said-

“...After reaching home, I followed the guidance very strictly and isolated myself for two weeks...”

He also added:

“People from my village only promote and spread negativity. So, I planned to mind my own business and not to get involved in social matters.”

Theme 2 : Minimization and Denial

This theme explores the defense mechanisms used by the participant while dealing with the period of infection. They tried to dismiss off their symptoms by thinking it was a normal flu and there was nothing to be afraid of.

The subordinate theme that emerged from the data was:

Coping Mechanism to Deal with Intense Emotions

Every participant expressed their emotions and how they dealt with it, during and after the infection. They have all used a variety of coping mechanisms to deal with these emotions. They either denied their illness and used various distractions to redirect their anxiety provoking thoughts related to the infection. Participants also

spoke about how they did not see their symptoms as being serious to a point where they acted like everything was fine.

Participant I said:

“I took it as just a fever, that will fade with paracetamol. It never crossed my mind that it was the dangerous Nipah fever, I never thought that way”

He also said:

“I enjoy cricket. I watched the game during hospital days. Also, my friends used to message to keep company”

Participant II said:

“I went to the hospital thinking it was a common flu... I had vomiting while resting at home, and I didn't take it seriously. I thought everyone goes through changes when one is sick...”

Participant III related a similar experience:

“I understood that I was in a multi-specialty hospital, I was thinking whether it was necessary to be admitted in a hospital like this for a normal fever”.

Theme 3: Being a Patient

This theme explores how the participants viewed being affected by an infection, and their aversion/fear/displeasure towards being a patient. It explains how

participants were afraid of being stuck in a patient role. The following subordinate themes had emerged from the data:

1. Fear of getting infected
2. Need for normality

Fear of getting Infected

The participants, on several occasions, spoke about how they had a fear of being a patient; of being someone who is sick; and eventually being stuck as a patient for the rest of their lives. The participants also spoke about a displeasure with being in a hospital setting.

An excerpt from the transcript of participant III read:

“...One day, before shifting me to the room, I was taken for an MRI scanning. When they tried me to lay me down, I just couldn’t because I was too scared. They would lock my head with a helmet-like thing for around 10 minutes. I was tensed thinking I will be trapped in that closed machine...”

Participant I said:

“...from the third day onwards, I was only thinking about when I would get discharged...”

He also said:

“...I was thinking about how I could go home, and that made me feel very happy...”

Need for Normality

The participants expressed how they wanted to go back home soon, to their normal life. They spoke about how they thought that they could go back home the second day itself.

Participant I said:

“...When I went to the hospital, I thought I would get discharged the next day...I was ready to go back home the next day itself, but when I was told that it was the protocol to be followed...”

He also said:

“...I was confident that I wouldn't fall sick again. Only my first result was positive, the rest two were negative. Also, I didn't have fever or anything...”

Theme 4: Fantasies and Emotional Reasoning

This theme explores the various unrealistic fantasies, that were driven by their emotions and gut feelings, that the participants had used to cope during the period of infection.

The subordinate theme that had emerged from the data was:

1. Unrealistic Predictions

Unrealistic Predictions

It was found from the study that many participants had engaged in building unrealistic beliefs about their illness. They had formed certain beliefs based on their gut feelings while they started showing initial symptoms. They spoke about how they felt that their symptoms didn't point to a normal fever, and with each passing day, they felt like things were getting complicated.

Participant I Said-

"...Even before the virus had infected me, I could understand that this was going to be severe..."

Participant III said something similar:

"... My mental state was not the same as when I get a normal fever. I had told my mom that this time the fever was going to be very severe. Even before knowing what fever it was. My mind told me that it was going to be very severe..."

Theme 5: Search for a Secure Base

This theme explores the various people/places that instilled a feeling of security and confidence in them.

The following subordinate themes emerged from the data-

1. Reliance on caregivers
2. Health workers as angels

3. Rage

Reliance on Caregivers

It could be derived from the study that the participants were always on the lookout for someone to derive strength from. Just knowing that their family was out there, supporting them, put them at ease. They expressed how being in proximity with or just seeing their parents gave them a lot of peace and comfort.

An excerpt from the transcript of participant II

"...I never felt alone while staying in the ward, my parents were always with me...my mom and dad were always with me, not just them, my entire family was with me..."

She said:

"...when I was at home under quarantine my entire family was there with me, I never had to feel alone..."

She also said:

"...during that time (ICU), I understood the value of family. I realised how my family would always stand by me, that they would never leave my side..."

"...When I was lying unconscious in the ICU, it was my family that experienced this entire situation. They were the ones who saw infected people being brought in, and also hearing about them dying right then..."

Health workers as Angels

The transcripts revealed how the participants viewed health care providers as angels, the ones who'd alleviate them from their illness. This reliance on them can be implied to their need to feel secure, and how health care workers gave them this security during the course of the illness.

An excerpt from the transcript of participant I read:

"...There were a lot of nurses to help me. All of them treated me very well. It was then that I understood the meaning of the word angels. They would always ask me about how I was feeling, and they were always so helpful..."

He also said:

"...every time, the one person who was always there at the right time was this Chandni Madam (Head, Dept of Emergency Medicine). Madam would personally come to my room and offer me support throughout..."

Participant II said something similar:

"...I was able to recover from this dangerous virus attack only because of the efforts of the doctors and the nurses that stood by me, they worked so hard to bring me back to life...."

Rage

This theme reveals how participants had used rage or anger to redirect their anxiety about the illness, thereby making them feel at least a little bit secure.

Participant III said:

“IV (Intravenous Therapy) was flowing through my veins even at 3 in the morning. It was the last bottle, my impatience overruled me and in the heat of the moment, I grabbed on the IV tubes with the needle and pulled it away from my hand. The sting of the needle hurt me bad”.

Theme 6: Profound Nature of the Experience

This theme explores how the experience of being contracted with the virus and all that followed, left profound impacts on the lives of the participants.

The following subordinate themes had emerged from the data:

1. Positive experience for life
2. Physical symptoms of the illness
3. Centre of attention

Positive experience

Both the participants I and II explained the positive life experiences they had got because of the illness.

Participant I said:

"...I understood the real meaning of life, that life experience. I got such a life experience at the age of 26..."

Physical symptoms of the illness

This theme explores the participant's experience with different symptoms of the illness they had to face. They spoke about how they were mostly unconscious, and would vomit a lot.

Participant II said:

"I was unconscious the whole time... I was lying in the ICU, unaware of the outside world. I opened my eyes to see health workers in PPE kits. Even then I was oblivious of the deadly virus roaming the town!"

Participant III said:

"My mother told me to sit and rest there, I lay down there, then I woke up on June 9th."

Centre of attention

Participants spoke about how they had become the centre of attention when they got the disease. They related experiences of how many people would keep coming to see them. It could be implied that having so many doctors and people coming to see them, made them feel like they were the centre of attraction, and this might have been one of the ways in which they coped with the illness.

Participant I said:

"...to be able to see people like Shylaja Madam was a great experience..."

Participant III also spoke along the same lines:

"... While I was sick, I could see how people would keep coming to see me..."

He also said:

"... Then doctors from Kalamassery had come. Doctors from many sections had come to see me...Even the DMO had come to see me and ask about whether I'd eaten some fruits while I was at Idukki...Even Shailaja teacher had come to see me and asked if we could arrange a program here..."

He further said:

"... When I was taken to get a scan, I could hear people saying oh isn't this the child that has the illness, and all that..."

DISCUSSION

In this chapter the findings of the present study is discussed in detail in comparison with the existing literature under following headings:

- Superordinate Themes
- Implications of the Present Study
- Recommendations for Future Researches
- Limitations of the Study

The present study aims at understanding how the survivors of the deadly Nipah virus that happened in Kerala made sense of their experience. Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) was the method selected for the study. After the analysis of data gathered from a sample of three participants , six superordinate themes had emerged. Even though the amount of literature available in the present area of study is very less, there have been considerable efforts to find out the underlying psychosocial factors of survivors of deadly illness. The available literature that could augment the understanding of the findings of the present study are discussed here.

The Dimension of Distance

The first super ordinate theme that emerged after the analysis of the data is the Dimension of Distance. It represents the distancing they experienced from the other people, and even the distance they kept from others to not to spread the disease. This is in relation to their experience of being socially discriminated, and having to be isolated from others due to the illness. Two subordinate themes

clustered under this superordinate theme. They are Distanced by others and Distanced from others. It is clear from the analysis that, the participants had to experience distancing from and by others.

Lithin et al. had conducted a study to explore the psychosocial perspective of Nipah virus outbreak in Kerala, India. Results found that the participants and their family had to face social ostracization following the illness. The study found that participants had a fear of transmitting the illness to other people and thus engaged in distancing and self-isolation. The study had highlighted the importance of psychosocial intervention along with the efforts in viral mitigation.

Minimization and Denial

This super ordinate theme contains the defense mechanisms used by the participant while dealing with the period of infection. The major aspects revealed about the survival of the illness is the use of Coping mechanism to deal with the intense Emotions. People who survived the virus had an awareness about the situation causing stress and they all had conscious attempts to eliminate the stress using a variety of coping mechanisms. Even they denied or they minimized the stress.

The finding of Shulamith Kreitler in the article named ‘Denial in Cancer Patients: Psychosocial Issues’ (28) runs in accordance with the findings of present study. Using of Denial as coping mechanism is found in the present study. The study deals with the role and functions of denial in cancer. Major conclusion this article made is that denial may have a positive effect when applied in the first phase of coping, after diagnosis, because it reduces anxiety. This holds also for the terminal

stage. Researchers also found some negative effects of denial; that it may interfere with getting treatment like delay in going to the doctor, not showing up for follow-ups, noncompliance, that may disrupt the process of assimilating the stressful event, may affect adversely interpersonal relations, and constitutes a cumulative stressor depressing even immunocompetence. The use of denial varies with the severity of the situation, the patient's personality, and his or her familial and cultural background.

Being a Patient

This superordinate theme explores the fear of the participants about being stuck in a patient role. This theme contains the participants frustration and discomforts regarding cemented in the patient's role and their desire to go back to their normal life. Two subordinate themes had emerged from the data. They are: Fear of getting infected, Need for normality. Participants expressed fear of eventually being stuck as a patient for the rest of their lives and expressed the desire to go back home soon, to their normal life.

It is found to be very hard to substantiate articles related to this theme. An article named 'Where all the patients? Addressing Covid-19 fear to encourage sick patients to seek emergency care' (29) found that the Emergency department volume is down nearly 50% as the United States struggles with the Covid-19 epidemic. There is increasing evidence that patients with medical emergencies are avoiding the emergency department because of fear of contracting Covid-19, In

this study the authors describe efforts taken in a community hospital to understand and combat this public health concern by using human-centered design.

The overarching theme from these interviews was fear. These findings are in line with the findings of present research as well.

Fantasies and Emotional Reasoning

This super ordinate theme contains the various unrealistic fantasies, that were driven by their emotions and gut feelings, that the participants had used to cope during the period of infection. The subordinate theme under this theme is unrealistic Predictions. Many participants build unrealistic beliefs about their illness. They had gut feelings based on emotional basis regarding the illness which others may find to be unrealistic.

The study of Johan Verwoerd et al. Emotional reasoning named “‘If I feel Disgusted, I Must Be Getting Ill’”: Emotional Reasoning in the Context of Contamination Fear’ (30) explains about the Patients suffering from anxiety disorders have been shown to infer danger on the basis of their anxiety responses “‘if I feel anxious, there must be danger.” This tendency logically hampers the identification of false alarms and may thus act in a way to confirm the a priori threat value of the feared stimuli/situations. This study tested whether indeed disgust-based reasoning might be involved in fear of contamination. And the Results showed that specifically in situations low in objective threat, contamination fearful individuals used disgust-response information to infer an increased risk of becoming ill. This is in line with the present study.

Search for a Secure Base

This theme explores the various people/places that instilled a feeling of security and confidence in the participants during the course of illness. The subordinate themes clubbed under this theme are: Reliance on caregivers, Health workers as angels and Rage. The study shows that the participants were always on the lookout for someone to derive strength from. They expressed the peace and comfort they received when there are people to support them. Even if it is the caregivers or the health care workers; they just search for a secure base in them during the course of illness. And the use of rage or anger helped them to redirect their anxiety and frustration about the illness, thereby making themselves feel better and to feel a little bit secure.

Niuniu Sun et al. conducted a qualitative study on the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during hospitalization (31) using phenomenological and robust sampling approach. They summarized the psychological experience into five themes. Firstly, attitudes toward the disease included fear, denial, and stigma during the early stages, which gradually developed into acceptance in the later stages. Secondly, the major source of stress included the viral nature of the disease, quarantine measures, and concerns regarding the health of family members. Thirdly, reactions of body and mind included disease stage-dependent emotional responses, excessive attention to symptoms, rumination, and changes in diet, sleep, and behavior. Fourthly, supportive factors included psychological adjustments, medical care, and family and social support. Finally, the disease resulted in

psychological growth and patients viewed problems with gratitude through the cherishing of life, family, bravery, and tenacity. And they also found that Negative emotions dominated during the early stages but gradually gave way to mixed positive and negative emotions.

The existing literature in this area clearly supports the important theme in this.

Profound Nature of the Experience

The major subordinate themes emerged after the analysis were Positive experience for life, Physical symptoms of the illness and Centre of attention. This superordinate theme explains the Profound nature of the experiences gained through the period of illness and recovery and the intense impacts it had on the lives of the participants. Participants had spoken about the positive experiences that had emerged out of their illness; such as meeting important people, and also the strength gained out of experiencing an epidemic such as this at such a young age.

Previous studies that had similar findings were found. The findings of a study named Lived experiences of Indian youth amid COVID-19 crisis: An Interpretative phenomenological analysis done by Alina suhail et al. (23) also mentions about the positive experiences they emerged out of their illness. The authors did an in-depth analysis of the lived experiences of Indian youth amid COVID-19 crisis and its impact on their mental health by interviewing ten college going students by using a semi-structured interview schedule to elicit participants' experiences with COVID-19 and the impact it has posed on their mental health.

Transcripts were analyzed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). Alina suhail et al. identified three master themes that emerged out of their research. Which were: Impact on mental health, Positive experiences and Ways of coping amid the crisis. The theme of positive experiences is in line with the present study.

SUMMARY

Kerala never had an experience like a sudden virus spread with intense fear. Kerala, especially Calicut has isolated during this time. All most all the patients were died and a huge panic was created as this is a deadly virus and there is no vaccination for this illness. Almost 17 lives have lost. This have made lasting impacts on the lives of people who have experienced it. It has deep impact on the psychosocial wellbeing of the survivors. This study aims to understand the experiences of survivors of Kerala Nipah virus and evaluate how these survivors made sense of their experience. The study uses the method of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) model developed by Pietkiewicz & Smith (24). A sample of three subjects was collected using Purposive Sampling Method. Data collected by semi structured interviews through Phone calls. Pietkiewicz & Smith Model is used for analysis. The study has found six super ordinate themes – The dimension of distance, Minimization and denial, Fantasies and emotional reasoning, Search for a secure base, Being a patient, Profound nature of the experience.

CONCLUSION

This present study focuses on the experiences of Survivors of Kerala Nipah virus attack identified six super ordinate themes; The dimension of distance, Minimization and denial, Fantasies and emotional reasoning, Search for a secure base, Being a patient and Profound nature of the experience. This study indicates

Psychosocial interventions for patients and their family members for during and after the hospitalization.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The Minimization and denial, Fantasies and emotional reasoning and fear of being a patient which includes various psychological aspects can be used in evaluating and extending the existing understanding and theoretical frame works regarding coping mechanisms, Emotional reasoning, fear of being a patient and the profound experiences as a survivor.
- The dimension of distance which includes the social aspects found in the research could be useful in developing a community-based intervention to address the issues regarding decreased social connectedness, to deal with social stigma could be designed new innovative interventions to improve this.
- This study indicates Psychosocial interventions for patients and their family members for during and after the hospitalization.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- The present study is the first of its kind which analyses the Nipah that happened in Kerala. This could be considered as a first step in IPA researches aiming to understand the experience of survivors of Kerala Nipah virus.
- Future studies could address specific factors such as the dimension of distance, being a patient and minimization and denial, fantasies and emotional reasoning to gain a broader understanding of the issues that the participants went through.

- This study recommends Psychosocial interventions for patients and their family members for during the hospitalization.
- The interventions should include family support and frequent follow ups.
- Different research tools could be developed to quantitatively analyses the themes emerged in this study.
- The researcher has used the technique of free association to interpret the data. Future studies could make use of other interpretative strategies.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The data collection was not done face to face due to Covid-19 protocol. Telephonic interview couldn't exactly seize their facial expressions when they talk about the experiences they went through.
- The participants had huge physical symptoms and was unconscious during the period of hospitalization. So, couldn't get the data during that period. Their emotions and thoughts while they were in ICU was lacking.
- Data were collected through phone calls and loss of network connection during the interview might have spoiled their emotional expression.
- The participant from the second outbreak had an emotional turmoil as compared to the other two, as it is too fast for him to attend an interview.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization, 2018
2. Gurley ES, Montgomery JM, Hossain MJ, Bell M, Azad AK, Islam MR, Molla MA, Carroll DS, Ksiazek TG, Rota PA, Lowe L. Person-to-person transmission of Nipah virus in a Bangladeshi community. *Emerging infectious diseases*. 2007 Jul;13(7):1031.
3. Chua KB. Nipah virus outbreak in Malaysia. *Journal of Clinical Virology*. 2003 Apr 1;26(3):265-75.
4. Paton NI, Leo YS, Zaki SR, Auchus AP, Lee KE, Ling AE, Chew SK, Ang B, Rollin PE, Umaphathi T, Sng I. Outbreak of Nipah-virus infection among abattoir workers in Singapore. *The Lancet*. 1999 Oct 9;354(9186):1253-6.
5. Uppal PK. Emergence of Nipah virus in Malaysia. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*. 2000 Dec;916(1):354-7.
6. Field H, Young P, Yob JM, Mills J, Hall L, Mackenzie J. The natural history of Hendra and Nipah viruses. *Microbes and infection*. 2001 Apr 1;3(4):307-14.
7. Thomas B, Chandran P, Lilabi MP, George B, Sivakumar CP, Jayadev VK, Bindu V, Rajasi RS, Vijayan B, Mohandas A, Hafeez N. Nipah virus infection in Kozhikode, Kerala, South India, in 2018: Epidemiology of an outbreak of an emerging disease. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine: Official Publication of Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*. 2019 Oct;44(4):383.
8. Chandni R, Renjith TP, Fazal A, Yoosef N, Ashhar C, Thulaseedharan NK, Suraj KP, Sreejith MK, Sajeeth Kumar KG, Rajendran VR, Remla Bevi A. Clinical

- Manifestations of Nipah Virus–Infected Patients Who Presented to the Emergency Department During an Outbreak in Kerala State in India, May 2018. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2020 Jun 24;71(1):152-7.
9. Swathi MS. Current Scenario of Nipah virus: A Review. 2019.
 10. Lithin Z, Harikrishnan U, Jayakumar C, Sekar K. Psychosocial Perspective of Nipah Virus Outbreak in Kerala, India. *International Journal of Scientific Study*. 2019;6(11): 159-162
 11. Melchert TP. Foundations of professional psychology: The end of theoretical orientations and the emergence of the biopsychosocial approach. Elsevier; 2011 Jul 12.
 12. Chua SE, Cheung V, Cheung C, McAlonan GM, Wong JW, Cheung EP, Chan MT, Wong MM, Tang SW, Choy KM, Wong MK. Psychological effects of the SARS outbreak in Hong Kong on high-risk health care workers. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*. 2004 Jun;49(6):391-3.
 13. Swathy, S. S., Sidharthan, M., Issudeen, M., Shibukumar, T. M., Kumar, A., & Tharayil, H. M. (2018). Psychological interventions during nipah viral outbreak in Kozhikode District, 2018. *Indian journal of psychological medicine*, 40(4), 387-389.
 14. Engel N, Ganesh G, Patil M, Yellappa V, Pai NP, Vadnais C, Pai M. Barriers to point-of-care testing in India: results from qualitative research across different settings, users and major diseases. *PLoS One*. 2015 Aug 14;10(8):e0135112.

15. Gardner PJ, Moallem P. Psychological impact on SARS survivors: Critical review of the English language literature. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie canadienne*. 2015 Feb;56(1):123.
16. Ventura-Garcia L, Roura M, Pell C, Posada E, Gascón J, Aldasoro E, Muñoz J, Pool R. Socio-cultural aspects of Chagas disease: a systematic review of qualitative research. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2013 Sep 12;7(9):e2410
17. Walter FM, Emery J, Braithwaite D, Marteau TM. Lay understanding of familial risk of common chronic diseases: a systematic review and synthesis of qualitative research. *The Annals of Family Medicine*. 2004 Nov 1;2(6):583-94.
18. Bray M, Geisbert TW. Ebola virus: the role of macrophages and dendritic cells in the pathogenesis of Ebola hemorrhagic fever. *The international journal of biochemistry & cell biology*. 2005 Aug 1;37(8):1560-6.
19. Hugo M, Declerck H, Fitzpatrick G, Severy N, Gbabei OB, Decroo T. Post-traumatic stress reactions in Ebola virus disease survivors in Sierra Leone. *Emerg Med (Los Angel)*. 2015;5(6)
20. Lee AM, Wong JG, McAlonan GM, Cheung V, Cheung C, Sham PC, Chu CM, Wong PC, Tsang KW, Chua SE. Stress and psychological distress among SARS survivors 1 year after the outbreak. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*. 2007 Apr;52(4):233-40.
21. Reissman DB, Arias I, Whitney EA, Taylor TH. Posttraumatic Stress Among Survivors of Bioterrorism—Reply. *JAMA*. 2004 Aug 4;292(5):566-.

22. Sun N, Wei L, Wang H, Wang X, Gao M, Hu X, Shi S. Qualitative study of the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during hospitalization. *Journal of affective disorders*. 2020 Aug 24;278:15-22.
23. Suhail A, Iqbal N, Smith J. Lived experiences of Indian Youth amid COVID-19 crisis: An interpretative phenomenological analysis. *The International Journal of Social Psychiatry*. 2020 Oct 11.
24. Pietkiewicz I, Smith JA. A practical guide to using interpretative phenomenological analysis in qualitative research psychology. *Psychological journal*. 2014;20(1):7-14.
25. Eatough V, Smith JA. Interpretative phenomenological analysis. *The Sage handbook of qualitative research in psychology*. 2008;179:194.
26. Arunkumar G, Chandni R, Mourya DT, Singh SK, Sadanandan R, Sudan P, Bhargava B. Outbreak investigation of Nipah virus disease in Kerala, India, 2018. *The Journal of infectious diseases*. 2019 May 24;219(12):1867-78.
27. Kreitler S. Denial in cancer patients: Psychosocial issues. *Cancer investigation*. 1999 Jan 1;17(7):514-34.
28. Wong Laura E, Hawkins Jessica E, Murrell Karen L. Where are all the patients? Addressing Covid-19 fear to encourage sick patients to seek emergency care. *NEJM Catalyst Innovations in Care Delivery*. 2020 May 14.
29. Verwoerd J, de Jong PJ, Wessel I, van Hout WJ. "If I feel disgusted, I must be getting ill": Emotional reasoning in the context of contamination fear. *Behaviour research and therapy*. 2013 Mar 1;51(3):122-7.

30. Verwoerd J, de Jong PJ, Wessel I, van Hout WJ. “If I feel disgusted, I must be getting ill”: Emotional reasoning in the context of contamination fear. *Behaviour research and therapy*. 2013 Mar 1;51(3):122-7.
31. Sun N, Wei L, Wang H, Wang X, Gao M, Hu X, Shi S. Qualitative study of the psychological experience of COVID-19 patients during hospitalization. *Journal of affective disorders*. 2020 Aug 24;278:15-22.